

FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF MICRO-FIBRILLATED CELLULOSE AND RUBBER NANOPARTICLE HYBRID EPOXY RESIN REINFORCED CARBON PLAIN WEAVE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The present work gives a contribution on understanding the effects of hybrid epoxy resins, enhanced with micro-fibrillated cellulose (MFC) and carboxylated nitrile-butadiene rubber nanoparticles (XNBR), on the tensile-tensile cyclic loading of carbon fibres plain weave textile composites. The experimental investigation shows the effects of four different combinations of MFC and XNBR weight contents in the epoxy resin (from 0% to 0.5% of MFC and from 0% to 3% of XNBR) on the fatigue behaviour compared to the composite with pure resin counterpart. The results of fatigue tests reveal on one hand a considerable extension of the fatigue life of the composite having the larger content of MFC, while a reduction increasing the XNBR weight. On the other hand, some combinations of MFC and XNBR delay the stiffness degradation of the composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Despite the extensive theoretical and experimental knowledge, detailed in the literature (see e.g. [1]), the mechanical performance of composite materials needs to be improved in some aspects to be really competitive with metallic materials such as super aluminium alloys. Composites suffer the potential risk of extension the internal defects under fatigue and impact loadings, due to the brittle nature of epoxy resins. Over the past decades, research efforts were dedicated to the development of toughened fibre-matrix composites, with basically two distinct approaches [2]. The first approach is based on 3D fibre reinforcement using advanced textile techniques [1] (e.g. stitching, z-pinning, waving, braiding, knitting, etc.). The second approach involves the modification of epoxy resins to get improved toughness. Modified thermosetting matrix resins have been created by the dispersion of a second phase normally consisting of nano- or micro- sized fillers (such as nanotubes, nano-fibres, nano-particles, rubber, etc) (see e.g. [3], [4]). Fillers are expected to generate extrinsic toughening mechanisms [5] and, as consequence, to affect the mechanical behaviour of fibre reinforced composite materials.

The identification of nano-sized cellulose micro-fibrils, named micro-fibrillated cellulose (MFC) [6] increased the range of hybrid nano-enhanced composite materials [7]. Cellulose is the most abundant natural homopolymer and one of the most promising renewable and environmentally friendly resources [8]. The effect on tensile properties and fracture toughness of micro-fibrillated cellulose-based epoxy reinforced carbon plain woven was investigated in [9].

Some studies investigated the chemical modification of epoxy resin with reactive liquid rubber, particularly carboxyl-terminated butadiene acrylonitrile (CTBN) (see e.g. [10]). The micro-structure consists of an elastomeric phase dispersed in the epoxy matrix with the elastomeric particle diameter of few micro-meters. Epoxy matrix modified with micro-fibrillated cellulose and carboxyl-terminated

butadiene acrylonitrile as liquid rubber was adopted to improve the interfacial adhesion in plain woven carbon fibre composites [11].

The present work gives a contribution on understanding the effects of hybrid epoxy resins, enhanced with micro-fibrillated cellulose (MFC) and carboxylated nitrile-butadiene rubber nanoparticles (XNBR), on the tensile-tensile cyclic loading of carbon fibres plain weave textile composites.

The experimental investigation shows the effects of four different combinations of MFC and XNBR weight contents in the epoxy resin (from 0% to 0.5% of MFC and from 0% to 3% of XNBR) on the fatigue behaviour compared to the composite with pure resin counterpart.

Preliminary quasi-static tensile tests and inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS) tests were performed to select the four fillers contents adopted for fatigue testing [12]. The quasi-static tensile tests show an enhancement of the tensile strength, increasing the contents of MFC and XNBR, up to 10% of the unmodified composite. XNBR and a limited content of MFC generate a very effective improvement of the inter-laminar shear strength. The best performance was recorded with 0.1% MFC and 3% XNBR ($\approx +32\%$ with respect to the pure epoxy composite).

The results of fatigue tests, detailed in this paper, reveal a considerable extension of the fatigue life of the composite having the larger content of MFC, while a reduction increasing the XNBR weight. Moreover, some combinations of MFC and XNBR delay the stiffness degradation of the composite.

2 DETAILS OF THE FILLERS AND MANUFACTURING OF THE COMPOSITE

The composite material is an epoxy matrix reinforced with a carbon fabric. The matrix is enhanced with two fillers: (1) micro-fibrillated cellulose (MFC) (Celish KY100G, Daicel Chemical Industries, Ltd., Japan) whose transverse dimensions and longitudinal length are $5\div 20$ nm and from 10 nm to several mm, respectively; (2) nanoparticles of carboxylated nitrile-butadiene rubber (XNBR) (JSR Corporation Ltd., Japan) whose diameter is in the range $80 \div 200$ nm.

The reinforcement is a balanced carbon fibres plain weave textile (Pyrofil TR-3110-MS, Mitsubishi Rayon Co. Ltd., Japan, areal density 200 g/m^2). The carbon fibres have tensile strength of 4 GPa and Young's modulus of 240 GPa. The reinforcement was selected to have a higher fibres and matrix adhesion surface than for a unidirectional reinforcement and to increase the influence of the matrix on the mechanical behaviour of the composites.

The matrix resin system contains epoxy resin (E-828, Japan Epoxy Resins Co. Ltd., Japan) and a modified aliphatic polyamine as curing agent (JER cure-113, Japan Epoxy Resins Co. Ltd., Japan).

The water slurry containing 10% MFC nano fibres is firstly treated by solvent exchange with pure ethanol to remove water. MFC containing ethanol is filtered by Büchner funnel to obtain a sheet of MFC. Then, the filtered sheet is stirred with additional ethanol and the proper quantity of epoxy resin. They are mixed together for 15 minutes in a high speed homogenizer. In this phase, ethanol is used to decrease the epoxy viscosity and to have uniformly dispersed MFC. The ethanol is removed maintaining the mixture at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 120 hours.

XNBR nanoparticles are mixed with methyl ethyl ketone (MEK). The mixture is then placed on a magnetic stirrer at $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 hours to dissolve the rubber into MEK, and then added to MFC containing epoxy resin.

The mixture of epoxy, XNBR and MFC is blended again in a homogenizer. The correct amount of curing agent is added to the hybrid resin. The mixture is stirred and then degased in a vacuum oven.

For the preliminary experimental investigation (quasi-static tensile tests and inter laminar shear strength), twelve combinations were prepared varying the MFC and XNBR weight contents in the range $0 \div 0.5\%$ and $0 \div 3\%$, respectively.

The laminates was manufactured with eight layers of carbon fibre plain weave textile stacked for impregnation on a heating system keeping the temperature of $50\text{-}60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to reduce the viscosity of the matrix. The curing cycle in a hot press was: $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour and then $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 hours keeping a pressure of 2 MPa. The resulting laminates had thickness of 1.97 ± 0.06 mm and fibre volume fraction of $45.7 \pm 1.9\%$.

3 FEATURES OF THE FATIGUE TEST SETUP

The fatigue performance of the selected plain weave textile composites with the hybrid modification of the epoxy resin was experimentally investigated assuming specimens having total length of 200 mm, gage length of 100 mm and width of 25 mm. Tests were performed under constant stress amplitude, sinusoidal wave-form tensile-tensile loading and assuming the ratio $R = 0.1$ (ratio of the minimum to the maximum stress in the cycle). The frequency was set to 5 Hz. Three different maximum stress levels were considered: 80%, 75% and 70% of the ultimate static tensile stress (see [12]).

At least three specimens were tested for each stress level up to failure or run out after 2 million cycles.

During cyclic loading, the strain in the load direction was measured by an MTS extensometer (mod. 632.11C) with gage length of 20 mm.

Some tests were assisted with a high speed digital camera (Memrecam fx K3) acquiring frames at a frequency of 250 Hz. The images post-processing allowed the measurement of the full field strain on the external surface of the specimen during loading by the digital image correlation technique using the Vic-2D software [13]. For this purpose, the central part of the specimen for a length of about 30 mm was speckled with white and black acrylic paints.

4 RESULTS AND COMPARISONS

From the preliminary quasi-static tests, the composites with the best static performance were selected for the fatigue investigation. The considered combinations of fillers were five: XNBR = 3% and $0.1 \leq \text{MFC} \leq 0.5\%$ (materials J, K, L in Table 1); material D with the maximum content of MFC and no XNBR; material A with pure resin as reference.

MFC Content	XNBR Content	
	0%	3%
0.0%	A	
0.1%	J	
0.3%	K	
0.5%	D	L

Table 1: Fillers contents (weight %) and nomenclature of materials for cyclic tests.

4.1 Fatigue life

The fatigue tests performed in the considered stress range (three stress levels) enabled depicting the fatigue life diagram for each of the five selected composites. Figure 1a compares the fatigue life diagrams (number of cycles to failure versus maximum stresses (σ_{\max}) in the cycle), including the valid cyclic tests for each load level and the respective average static tensile strength [12] corresponding to the extrapolated lowest number of cycles, $N = 1$.

Appropriate fitting was adopted for the experimental data to have a reliable predicting of the fatigue life corresponding to other stress levels in the considered stress range, which were not directly determined by testing. The semi-logarithmic function adopted is $\sigma_{\max} = k \log N + a$, where N is the number of cycle to failure, while k and a are parameters to be defined by the least squares method. The fittings of the experimental results (run-outs are not included) are compared in Figure 1b. The curves in Figure 1b have the coefficient of correlation in the range $0.94 \div 0.98$. This confirms the reliability of the fittings.

Figure 2 shows the slope of the linear fitting curves (see Figure 1b). Similar values are for the composites A, D and J while a 10% higher is for materials K and L. This predicts a fast reduction of the fatigue life for composites containing the higher contents of both MFC and XNBR than that of the composites with only MFC. This is visible comparing the average number of cycles to failure for the maximum and minimum applied load levels. For the lowest load level (σ_{\max} 80% of σ_u , Figure 3a) the

fatigue life of composites with mix of the two fillers (J, K and L) is comparable to the unmodified material (A) and the composite containing only MFC (D). Decreasing the stress level (70% of σ_u), i.e. in the high cycles regime, the combination of the two fillers shortened the fatigue life (see Figure 3b). For the lowest stress level, the composite D, enhanced with the maximum content of MFC, shows the longer fatigue life than all the other composites including the unmodified one, as observed in [14].

Figure 1: (a) Fatigue life diagram for the five selected composites; (b) semi-logarithm fitting. '→' means no failure after 2 million cycles.

Figure 2: Slope of the linear fitting of the fatigue life curves.

Figure 3: Comparison of the average fatigue life for two maximum stress levels in the cycle: (a) 80%; (b) 70% of σ_u . '→' means no failure after 2 million cycles.

The fatigue damage development in composite materials may be described by empirical metrics. One of the main adopted damage metric is the stiffness degradation [15]. In the present investigation, the stiffness is selected as the slope of the segment passing through the points of maximum and minimum of the stress-strain cycle curve.

For the sake of comparison, the degradation of the stiffness (i.e. the development of the imparted damage) is presented assuming the ratio of the cycle stiffness at the current cycle n and the initial stiffness (named “stiffness ratio”), and the fractional life (named “cycles ratio”) defined as the ratio n/N_f , being N_f the fatigue life [15].

For the highest stress level (σ_{\max} 80% of σ_u), the materials show a continuous almost linear degradation of the stiffness (Figure 4a), meaning a continuous development of the damage in the composites leading to failure. This behaviour is similar for all the hybrid modifications with an initial faster stiffness decrease for material L.

In the high cycles regime (σ_{\max} 70% of σ_u), the curves in Figure 4b highlights the typical three stage behaviour [15]. The first stage shows a rapid decrease of stiffness and demonstrates a fast development of the damage until a fractional life of about 0.15. In the initial stage, material L shows a lower slope of the curve, meaning a slowest diffusion of damage in the material, reaching the same stiffness ratio (≈ 0.85) of the other materials in almost 35% of the fatigue life. The second stage is almost linear with a very low decrease of the stiffness until a fractional life of about 0.9. The third and final stage shows a fast decrease of the stiffness of all materials as consequence of a rapid spread of the damage until failure (not visible for specimens of material D, no failure after 2 million cycles).

Figure 4: Stiffness ratio vs. cycles ratio for two stress levels: (a) 80% and (b) 70% of σ_u .

4.2 Damage observations

The damage imparted during cyclic loading was observed by SEM (scanning electron microscope) on specimens cyclically loaded with $\sigma_{\max} = 80\% \sigma_u$. Images of the fracture surfaces were recorded for composite A, D and J.

Two main differences of the fracture surfaces are relevant: the matrix deformation and the residual matrix on the fibres surface. The material with unmodified resin (A) has relatively smooth and glassy epoxy matrix (see left image in Figure 5a), typical of a brittle thermosetting polymer [16]. The content of MFC in composite D generates an extensive “plastic” deformation of the matrix (see left image in Figure 5b). This is the first motivation for the longer fatigue life of the composite enhanced with MFC. The combination of MFC and XNBR increases the “plastic” deformation of the matrix (see rough matrix fracture surface in the left image of Figure 5c for material J) with respect to the unmodified composite (A). But probably, this is not enough to extend the fatigue life. The fatigue life of material J is similar to that of composite A (see Figure 3). Observing the surface of the fibres, in the unmodified

composite (A) the fibres do not have residual resin in adhesion (see right image in Figure 5a). The effect of MFC at fibre/matrix interface is clear in material D. The broken fibres show good adhesion to matrix (see right image in Figure 5b). This is the second reason for the longer fatigue life of the composite with MFC (D). The composite with matrix including both MFC and XNBR had several fibre/matrix debondings (see right image in Figure 5c) and, as consequence, the fatigue life is not improved.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5: SEM pictures of the fracture surface of specimens cyclically loaded with $\sigma_{\max} = 80\% \sigma_u$. Composite (a) A, (b) D and (c) J.

5 COCNLUSIONS

The present work intended to understand the effects of hybrid epoxy resins, enhanced with microfibrillated cellulose (MFC) and carboxylated nitrile-butadiene rubber nanoparticles (XNBR), on the tensile-tensile cyclic loading of carbon fibres plain weave textile composites.

The main results of the investigation are the following.

The fatigue life of composites containing the hybrid matrix with the higher contents of MFC and XNBR had a faster reduction than that of the composites with only MFC.

The best performance was observed for the composite enhanced with only MFC. The combination of the two fillers generated a fatigue life almost similar to the unmodified material at the highest stress level and a reduction of the fatigue life for the lowest stress level.

The stiffness of the materials had similar degradation trend during the fatigue life, except the composite L (MFC 0.5%, XNBR 3%) subjected to the lowest cyclic stress level. In this, the imparted damage decreased the stiffness of 15% in almost 35% of the fatigue life, while the others got the same reduction in the initial 15% of the fatigue life.

SEM observations of the fracture surface of specimens cyclically loaded with $\sigma_{\max} = 80\% \sigma_u$ highlighted two main reasons for the better fatigue performance of material containing only MFC (D): the extensive “plastic” deformation of the matrix; the improved fibre and matrix adhesion.

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